

Factors Affecting Customer Satisfaction Of Retail Banking Services Of Commercial Banks In Dong Nai Province

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 01, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 01, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Customer, Satisfaction, Retail, Banking, Services, and LHU</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5367951</p>	<p><i>Retail banking service has always been considered a core activity. It has the effect of speeding up the cash flow process, taking advantage of the great potential of the capital of all economic sectors. It is to lend to improve people's living standards, limiting cash payments, and contributing to saving cost and time for both the banks and the customers. Besides, the development of retail banking services is in line with the inevitable trend in the operation of commercial banks in the region, in the world in general, and of Vietnamese commercial banks in particular. Therefore, the authors surveyed 750 customers using retail banking services. In addition, the article found out factors affecting customer satisfaction of retail banking services of commercial banks in Dong Nai province with one percent significance. The paper was applying structural equation modeling (SEM). Finally, the authors had policy recommendations to enhance customer satisfaction of retail banking services of commercial banks.</i></p>

Introduction

Begley, W. L. (2015) showed that the banking service plays an essential role in expanding the market, improving competitiveness, creating an important medium and long-term capital source for the bank, diversifying banking activities, and bringing in solid revenue. Secure, low-risk, diversified non-banking products and services, increasing and developing commercial banks' current and potential customer network.

The large population and rapid development of supermarkets, commercial centers, shopping centers, and convenience stores contribute to making the retail market the top concern of all businesses, including banks. Currently, Vietnam has about 97 million people, is the 15th most populous country in the world. According to the forecast of the Ministry of Industry and Trade, in 2020, the whole country will have about 1,500 supermarkets, 180 commercial centers, 157 shopping centers, and more than 1,500 convenience stores. It is an opportunity for the bank to restructure its revenue, gradually shift from credit service revenue to service revenue through developing and providing convenient banking products and services to meet the payment needs of the people.

Dougall, G. H. (2016) showed that developing banking services diversified types of services, meet the increasing demands of social actors, and promote economic growth and sustainable development. Retail banking services bring convenience, safety, and savings to businesses and people in the process of payment and use of their income. Retail banking service is a solid bridge between banks and customers in the present and the future. On the other hand, a well-developed Retail banking service will lead to the development of different types of services, creating a system of various products and services that actively support each other.

We are developing banking services, increasing capital circulation, contributing to the economy's growth and development, and ensuring proactive international economic integration. From the socio-economic perspective, the development of banking services affects the money circulation process, taking advantage of the great potential of capital for economic development by Paul, B. S. (2017). Retail banking service will shorten the transaction time between the bank and the customer, making the currency quickly transfer from the customer's hand to the bank and vice versa - the capital raised and reinvested soon to develop the economy, helping to improve people's living standards. Therefore, the article explores various factors affecting customer satisfaction of retail banking services of commercial banks in Dong Nai province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Customer satisfaction (Cs)

According to Sanz, B. S. (2019), customer satisfaction is the feedback of consumers, comments about the characteristics of products and services that they use. These reflections will show different levels of satisfaction when they consume products and services.

According to Bhattach K. A. (2017), customer satisfaction is the feeling state of a person derived from comparing the results obtained from consuming a product/service with those of the past. Customers' expectations formed from the shopping experience, from friends and colleagues, and information from sellers and competitors. Zhang, J. G. (2019) showed that satisfaction depends on the difference between received results and expectations if actual results are lower than expectations. Besides, customers are not satisfied; if actual results match expectations, customers will be happy. If the actual result is higher than the expectation, the customer is delighted by Albinsson, M. A. (2014).

From the above concepts, the authors believe that: Customer satisfaction with a service is the state of feeling that customers have because the service meets or does not meet their expectations. In other words, customer satisfaction is the result of the service meeting or not meeting the customer's needs by Johnson, M. F., and Roos, I. R. (2015).

Reliability(Rel)

Reliability refers to the ability to provide accurate, on-time, and reputable services. It requires consistent service performance and honoring commitments and promises to customers by Ostrom, A.L. (2012). Each employee must carry out the planning at work and clearly define the work to be done and arrange it to prioritize the tasks that need to be prioritized. Banks need to set up an automatic notification system to customers, customer information that is kept confidential increases customer satisfaction by Gronroos, C. (1984). In addition, Zhang, J. G. (2019) showed that reliability could perform services committed to customers, keep information well, and certain assets for customers by Fecikova I. S. (2014). Reliability in the service delivery process represents the ability of the bank to perform the service correctly the first time and the staff to limit errors in the implementation process. From that, we have the following hypothesis H1:

Hypothesis H1: Reliability (Rel) has a positive relationship with customer satisfaction with retail banking services.

Empathy(Emp)

Sympathy is the care, considerate customer care, giving customers the best thoughtful treatment to help customers feel that they are the "highest customer" of the bank and are always warmly welcomed, anytime, anywhere by Chen, S. W. (2018). The human factor is at the core of this success, and the more the bank cares about its customers, the more sympathy will be. Empathy is the care for customers of the staff. The bank staff are friendly, enthusiastic and treat all customers fairly by Gronroos, C. (1984). Customers want the bank to take care of themselves and their families, understand their particular needs and interests. The staff cares about customers. Employees understand the unique needs and benefits desired by customers to respond to customers' needs promptly. From that, we have the following hypothesis H2:

Hypothesis H2: Empathy (Emp) has a positive relationship with customer satisfaction with retail banking services.

Responsiveness (Res)

Responsiveness is a measure of the ability to solve problems quickly, effectively handle complaints, be ready to help customers, and respond to customer requests. In other words, responsiveness is the response from the service provider to what the customer wants by Chang, H. K. (2017). Responsiveness is the desire and willingness of employees to provide timely service to customers. Does the bank provide complete, convenient, and accurate information to customers, can solve problems quickly, effectively handle complaints and meet customer requirements by Gronroos, C. (1984). When there is a change in information during the transaction, the bank promptly informs the customer by Townen, J. H. and Vedges, R. L. (2018). From that, we have the following hypothesis H3:

Hypothesis H3: Responsiveness (Res) has a positive relationship with customer satisfaction with retail banking services.

Competence(Com)

Service capacity is the factor that creates trust and confidence for customers, which is felt through professional service, sound professional knowledge, polite demeanor, and good communication ability. Hence, Customers feel secure every time they use the bank's services by Kwon, S. J. (2019). Service capacity is expressed through professional qualifications to perform services by Vancheryl, S.K. (2017). The ability to

serve manifests when employees interact with customers, directly perform services, and research to capture relevant information necessary for customer service by Nilsson, D. H. (2005). The guarantee showed that the staff is trustworthy, polite, friendly, has professional knowledge, is always willing to help customers, and the bank has a flexible pricing policy. From that, we have the following hypothesis H4:

Hypothesis H4: Competence (Com) has a positive relationship with customer satisfaction with retail banking services.

Tangibles (Tan)

Tangibles: This element is the external image of the facility, the attitude of the staff, documents, manuals, and the bank's communication system. In general, everything that the customer can see directly with the eyes and senses can affect this factor by Gummerus, J., and San R. F. (2016). Tangible means reflected in the appearance, costumes of service staff, and facilities and equipmentserved the service by Parasuraman, A. (2000). The facilities are modern and comfortable, the transaction location is convenient, the staff uniforms are neat and polite. Modern equipment, reasonable layout of transaction counters, easy to identify by Hecker, T. R., & Francis, H. G. (2012). Good service facilities such as parking place, waiting for space. Neat and polite staff uniforms affecting customer satisfaction about retail banking services by Yang, H. R. (2014). From that, we have the following hypothesis H5:

Hypothesis H5: Tangibles (Tan) have a positive relationship with customer satisfaction with retail banking services.

With the above analysis, the proposed model is based on the research of Lin, D. B., & Yan, B. S. (2016) because this scale is applied in many areas of retail banking services and is shown in the proposed research model as follows:

Source: Researchers proposed

FIGURE 1
A RESEARCH MODEL FOR FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMER SATISFACTION OF RETAIL BANKING SERVICES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS

METHODS OF RESEARCH

The research process is as follows: first, it is necessary to study the theory of the scale, learn the theoretical bases of satisfaction and the factors affecting customer satisfaction. Based on that theoretical basis and based on the actual situation at the bank, the initial research model was proposed. Then the authors processed the research through two main phases. Phase 1: qualitative research and phase 2 quantitative research.

Source: Researchers proposed

FIGURE 2
A RESEARCH PROCESS FOR FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMER SATISFACTION OF RETAIL BANKING SERVICES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS

The purpose of the qualitative research phase is to provide preliminary issues affecting customer satisfaction when using retail banking services, thereby providing a scale for the concepts in the model. research form. Qualitative research is used in the exploratory phase. Data is collected in a qualitative form through discussion and interpretation techniques by Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., and Black, W. (2010). Exploratory research to clarify unknowns Preliminary research is a common way to reduce data collection errors and scale errors and increase the validity of the answer sheet.

The qualitative research phase aims to evaluate:

- + Assess the suitability and supplement the scales from the original set of scales.
- + Check the use of words in each question of each observed variable to ensure that most of the interviewees understand correctly and clearly.
- + Preliminarily check the correlation of the hypotheses proposed in the research model.

The first study was conducted through direct interviews with ten experts to clarify customer satisfaction using retail banking services and influencing factors. The authors are to check the level of clarity and word usage in the questionnaire about the content of the scales, preliminary survey followed by distributing the questionnaire directly to 10 customers to check wording errors before a formal investigation. The authors built the interview results into a standard questionnaire with explicit content and meaning, and the questions were easy to understand for most subjects for this study.

After adjusting the preliminary scale from qualitative research, the authors will officially use this scale in quantitative analysis. Quantitative research is applied to test the scale, determine the factors affecting customer satisfaction and each element's importance. In this study, the authors collect data and resolve relationships through numerical form and research from a deductive point of view, using scientific models. The authors can prove these quantitative research methods and objective reality. In addition, the authors' group of data collection was processed through SPSS 20.0 software with scale testing with Cronbach's Alpha, EFA, CFA, and analysis of the linear structural model (SEM).

Quantitative research aims to conduct sampling, a survey by questionnaire with a sample of 750 customers using banking services. The data collected from the survey questionnaire was processed with Excel raw data and then analyzed with SPSS 20.0 and Amos software. The authors conducted a field survey with 750 votes distributed and collected 735 valid votes, 15 missing information, and the pass rate was 98.00%. After checking, removing the votes with too many blanks, typing many options in the same statement, or typing all the comments with the same answer, the authors left with 735 valid votes. This study was conducted in 2021,

and the authors took survey data from January 2021 to April 2021. Finally, the authors had conclusions & managerial implications.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Testing of Cronbach's alpha

TABLE 1		
TESTING OF CRONBACH'S ALPHA FOR CUSTOMER SATISFACTION (CS)		
Code	Customer satisfaction (Cs)	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
CS1	In general, you are satisfied with the quality of retail banking services	0.946
CS2	You would recommend to your friends and family about retail banking	0.887
CS3	You would continue to use retail banking services soon	0.943
Cronbach's alpha: 0.949		

Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0

Table 1 showed that Cronbach's alpha for customer satisfaction (Cs) meets this technique's requirements. Specifically, Cronbach's Alpha values of the customer satisfaction (Cs) is 0.949, and Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted (>0.6).

TABLE 2		
TESTING OF CRONBACH'S ALPHA FOR RELIABILITY (REL)		
Code	Reliability (Rel)	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
REL1	You feel secure when using retail banking services	0.951
REL2	Retail banking execute transactions accurately, without errors	0.962
REL3	Retail banking staff keep customer information well protected	0.960
REL4	Retail banking deliver service at the time they've committed to customers	0.945
Cronbach's alpha: 0.966		

Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0

Table 2 showed that Cronbach's alpha for the reliability (Rel) meets this technique's requirements. Specifically, Cronbach's Alpha values of the reliability (Rel) is 0.966, and Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted (>0.6).

TABLE 3		
TESTING OF CRONBACH'S ALPHA FOR EMPATHY (EMP)		
Code	Empathy (Emp)	Cronbach's Alpha
EMP1	Retail banking always strive to build good relationships and pay attention to the needs of each customer	0.952
EMP2	Retail banking staffs are enthusiastic and friendly to customers	0.962
EMP3	Retail banking serve all customers fairly	0.965
EMP4	Retail banking staffs always ask, congratulate, give gifts to customers every holiday or personal event	0.951
Cronbach's alpha: 0.968		
Code	Responsiveness (Res)	Cronbach's Alpha
RES1	Retail banking staff always satisfactorily solve all difficulties, questions, complaints about customers	0.809
RES2	The time for customers to wait for a transaction is short (5-10 minutes) at retail banks	0.821
RES3	Simple transaction procedures at retail banks	0.855
RES4	Retail banks have a 24-hour hotline	0.812
Cronbach's alpha: 0.862		
Code	Competence (Com)	Cronbach's Alpha
Com1	Retail banking staffs handle transactions correctly, quickly, and efficiently	0.872
Com2	Retail banking staffs have sufficient knowledge and expertise to advise and answer customer inquiries	0.828
Com3	Retail banking staffs are always polite, considerate, and welcoming to customers	0.882
Com4	Retail banking staffs have a high reputation in the hearts of customers	0.868
Cronbach's alpha: 0.893		

Tangibles (Tan)		
Tan1	Retail banking has a spacious and convenient headquarters for customers	0.944
Tan2	Retail banking with modern equipment and machinery	0.942
Tan3	Papers, forms, vouchers used in banking transactions are designed to be simple and clear	0.951
Tan4	Retail banking staffs have a very professional manner and dress neatly and politely when communicating with customers	0.930
Cronbach's alpha: 0.956		

Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0

Table 3 showed that all of Cronbach's alpha is ≥ 0.6 . Cronbach's Alpha coefficient has a variable value in the interval [0,1]. The test results show a total correlation coefficient (≥ 0.3). Cronbach's Alpha coefficient ≥ 0.6 should meet the requirements of reliability.

TABLE 4 KMO AND BARTLETT'S TEST FOR FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMER SATISFACTION OF RETAIL BANKING SERVICES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.832
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	17759.039
	df	253
	Sig.	0.000
Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings: Cumulative is 85.077 %		

Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0

Table 4 showed that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy (KMO) is 0.832 (>0.5). This result is consistent with the actual data investigated by 750 customers using retail banking services of commercial banks. Cumulative is 85.077 %.

Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos

FIGURE 3
TESTING CFA FOR FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMER SATISFACTION OF RETAIL BANKING SERVICES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS

Figure 3 showed that the assessment of the scale of the customer satisfaction of retail banking services of commercial banks including: CMIN/DF = 4.018 (<5.0), GFI = 0.912 (>0.8), TLI = 0.957 (>0.9), CFI = 0.963 (>0.9) and RMSE = 0.064 (<0.08).

Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos

FIGURE 4
TESTING SEM FOR FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMER SATISFACTION OF RETAIL BANKING SERVICES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS

Relationships	Unstandardized Estimate	Standardized Estimate	SE.	CR.	P	Results
CS <--- REL	0.532	0.547	0.033	16.265	***	Accepted
CS <--- EMP	0.079	0.083	0.029	2.690	0.007	Accepted
CS <--- RES	0.186	0.173	0.035	5.282	***	Accepted
CS <--- COM	0.173	0.089	0.051	3.383	***	Accepted
CS <--- TAN	0.097	0.106	0.029	3.349	***	Accepted

Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos

Table 5 showed five factors affecting the customer satisfaction of retail banking services of commercial banks with a significance level of 0.01. The results showed that all five service qualities in the theoretical model.

Parameter	SE	SE-SE	Mean	Bias	SE-Bias
CS <--- REL	0.039	0.001	0.530	-0.001	0.001
CS <--- EMP	0.029	0.000	0.076	-0.003	0.001
CS <--- RES	0.039	0.001	0.182	-0.005	0.001
CS <--- COM	0.048	0.001	0.167	-0.005	0.001
CS <--- TAN	0.027	0.000	0.096	-0.001	0.001

Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos

Table 6 showed that the bootstrap test results are very good with a sample of 50.000 for the customer satisfaction of retail banking services of commercial banks.

CONCLUSION & MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Conclusion

Retail banking is always the core activity of commercial banks. Developing retail banking services will diversify service types, meet the increasing demands of social actors, and promote economic growth and sustainable development. In the market economy, the need for banking services, especially retail banking services, is increasing. The target of retail banking services is individual, household, and small and medium-sized enterprises. The benefits are usually simple, easy to implement, and regular, focusing on deposit services

and accounts, loans to buy cars, houses, opening credit cards, etc. As a result, many people who are not familiar with retail banking products and services in the future will participate in this field. The article found out factors affecting customer satisfaction of retail banking services of commercial banks in Dong Nai province with one percent significance. The paper was applying structural equation modeling (SEM). From 2021 to 2025, the banking sector will continue to have strong growth, including the retail banking service segment. The demand for retail banking services of businesses and people is increasing, making the orientation focus on developing retail banking services an inevitable trend, which is considered a development strategy. The focus of many banks is to diversify revenue sources, minimize operational risks and achieve maximum business efficiency. Finally, the authors had policy recommendations to enhance customer satisfaction of retail banking services of commercial banks.

Managerial implications

Accelerating the development of banking products and services on mobile phones and online banking with many new, convenient, fast, and increasingly friendly, and easy-to-use utilities for customers. (1) Managerial implications for improving the reliability (0.547). The Covid-19 epidemic has changed customers' psychology, consumption, and investment behavior, requiring credit institutions to reshape the way they provide products and services. Customers prefer to use them. They were using digital channels and e-commerce. Besides, retail banking should continue to focus on developing the retail segment based on the digital technology application platform. Finally, retail banking should focus on creating better customer experiences to enhance satisfaction, lead to loyalty, and aim for higher revenue from a specific audience. Retail banks also need to build a multi-interactive ecosystem to increase service quality and choice for customers and develop business activities and cross-sell products associated with new businesses. Conveniences of daily life.

(2) Managerial implications for improving the responsiveness (0.173). Retail banking should diversify banking products and services for customers. With a customer-centric model, banks need to develop specialized products and services for each specific target group. Strengthen training to improve professional qualifications and service quality. To provide customers with the best banking services, the movement of bank staff should focus on: products, services, and professional processes; professional discipline and work management capacity; soft skills at work; skills in customer care, analysis, consulting, and service strategy development. Finally, retail banking should improve the legal regulations governing banking activities are issued by many levels and agencies, which requires completing the legal environment in a comprehensive, synchronous, and unified manner in the direction of services. It is simple, easy to understand, convenient for use, in line with international practices and standards, and at the same time protect the legitimate interests of customers and the bank.

(3) Managerial implications for improving the tangibles (0.106). Retail banking should continue strengthening facilities and technology to provide retail banking services. Strengthen the application of advanced technology in line with the development level of the Vietnamese banking system male, develop an online trading system, and gradually expand the one-stop trading model. Commercial banks create a network of branches and transaction offices with a compact model to quickly increase capital quickly and effectively respond to the needs of banking services of the people. Strengthening linkages between commercial banks to expand card usage and promote ATM cards' practical features save costs and create convenience for customers. In addition to traditional distribution channels, it is necessary to apply modern distribution channels to meet the needs of transactions anytime, anywhere so that customers can use them, such as placing orders, making payments, querying information. They were based on commitments between the bank and the customer. They are developing banking services at home to take advantage of the development of computers and internet connectivity. Building banking transactions by phone is a popular model with meager cost, convenient for customers and banks. Customers can make transactions at any time, any place.

(4) Managerial implications for improving the competence (0.089). Retail banking services build their brand through communication activities, conveying information to the masses to help customers get updated information, a basic understanding of retail banking services, and the benefits of products. Banks need to segment the market to determine a reasonable market structure and target customers, group customers, according to appropriate criteria, thereby introducing suitable products for each customer. Banks need to regularly provide information on business results so that customers have confidence in the bank. Identify the needs of each customer group, thereby offering suitable products and services. Improve service quality, simplify procedures based on taking advantage of modern information technology (IT) to serve customers better. IT is the foundation for business development and expansion of new services to increase the application

of science and technology and advanced technology, developing an online trading system, and gradually implementing a trading model. Retail banking should continue modernizing all banking operations, ensuring integration with international banks in all fields. Enhance automatic processing in all processes of receiving customer requests, verifying and processing information, improving service quality, ensuring confidentiality and safety in business.

(5) Managerial implications for improving empathy (0.083). Diversify products and new distribution channels to diversify products, expand and develop consumer credit, enhance the attraction of remittances based on coordination with labor export companies, remittance service companies, overseas money transfer organizations, foreign correspondent banks. We have policies to exploit and create favorable conditions for remittance services through the banking system. Coordinate with study abroad companies to develop study abroad loan products. Strengthen cross-selling of products and services between banks and insurance, developing and expanding non-cash payment products and services, contributing to limiting illegal cash transactions, quickly improving the liquidity and efficient use of capital in the economy. Promote deposit account services with safe and straightforward procedures to attract personal capital in payment and develop card payment services, personal payment checks, promote capital mobilization through account savings. Retail banking also needs to strengthen cooperation with organizations and businesses with regular service payments, stabilize the number of customers, pay salaries such as post offices, airlines, electricity.

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